

Who gets represented? Age, gender and voting in Flemish municipalities

Lorenzo Catalano¹, Panagiotis Iliopoulos¹, Kristof De Witte^{1,2}

1. Faculty of Economics and Business, KU Leuven, Belgium
2. Maastricht University

Summary

1. This policy brief summarises evidence on whether candidates' characteristics - namely, age and gender - shape electoral outcomes in Flemish municipal elections.
2. The study uses an original dataset of 105,326 candidates across 300 municipalities in the 2006, 2012 and 2018 elections.
3. Findings show that candidates obtain better results in municipalities in which voters are closer to them in age.
4. Female candidates face a persistent electoral penalty, receiving fewer preferential votes than male candidates.
5. Female mayors reduce this penalty: in municipalities governed by female mayors, female candidates gain an extra 1 percentage point compared to female candidates in other municipalities.
6. Voting patterns also spread across neighbouring municipalities, suggesting that local representation can have wider spatial spillovers.

1. Introduction

Political competition increasingly revolves around identity-based narratives. In this context, the personal traits of candidates, such as age and gender, may become crucial factors in attracting voters. In Catalano et al. (2026), we examine whether descriptive representation shapes electoral outcomes in municipal elections in Flanders, Belgium. Descriptive representation refers to politicians sharing visible, ascriptive characteristics with

the people they represent, such as age or gender.

This question poses significant challenges to democratic regimes. If voters systematically reward candidates who resemble them, and if some groups face penalties despite formal equality rules, electoral outcomes may reproduce and perpetuate imbalances in political power. Flanders represents a compelling case study for multiple reasons. First, as the first country to introduce gender quotas across all levels of government, Belgium has a long-standing commitment to

gender equality. Second, the region displays ageing population patterns common to many Western countries. Third, municipal elections feature preference voting, allowing citizens to support individual candidates directly. Fourth, the region presents a strong nationalist sentiment. The literature suggests that voters have limited attention. Therefore, if descriptive representation remains valued in this context - where the quest for autonomy imposes a significant cognitive load and gender equality is already deeply entrenched - we can expect it to be relevant in a wide variety of other settings.

The study focuses on two dimensions: age and gender. Regarding gender, Flemish municipal electoral law requires parity on candidate lists and gender alternation in the top positions. Yet, progress has slowed at the local level, and women still occupied fewer than 30% of first list positions in most parties by 2018.

The age dimension is also pressing. The share of young candidates aged 18-34 has declined faster than in the general population, while candidates aged 65 and older have increased more rapidly. This trend raises concerns that younger generations may become less visible in municipal councils.

2. Data and Methodology

The study analyses three municipal elections in Flanders, held in 2006, 2012 and 2018. The dataset includes 105,326 candidates across 300 municipalities. It combines candidate-level electoral data from the Flemish regional government with information on candidates' age, gender, preferential votes, party, election outcomes and appointments to the mayorship. We track candidates across election cycles and consider municipal factors such as population size, unemployment,

immigration inflows, the share of residents with foreign origins, and child poverty.

The main outcome is each candidate's vote share within their party. This measure captures the number of preferential votes a candidate receives as a share of all votes cast for their party. This helps isolate the role of personal characteristics from the overall party success.

The analysis has three steps. **First**, it examines whether age and gender are associated with candidates' vote shares. **Second**, it studies whether the presence of a female mayor affects the electoral performance of female candidates in later elections. **Third**, it investigates whether voting patterns in one municipality are influenced by neighbouring municipalities and by earlier elections. This allows the study to capture not only local effects, but also whether representation dynamics spread across space and persist over time.

3. Results

The results show that descriptive representation matters in Flemish municipal elections. Age proximity between candidates and voters improves their electoral performance: voters systematically favour candidates who are closer to them in age. The study finds that when the share of residents in a candidate's age group is lower, that candidate's vote share also falls. For example, a 10-percentage-point reduction in the share of residents in the candidate's age group is associated with a 0.67 percentage-point fall in vote share.

This result is especially relevant for young candidates. The paper finds that candidates under 35 are most affected by age proximity with their electorate. Combined with the

declining share of young candidates and an ageing population, this suggests a likely decrease in the share of young municipal councillors. This may weaken attention to policies relevant to younger generations.

The gender results are equally important. Female candidates face a clear electoral penalty. On average, women receive about 3 percentage points fewer votes than their male counterparts. This finding is striking because it appears in a context with formal long-standing gender quotas and a relatively strong commitment to gender equality across sectors. It shows that gender discrimination requires further action.

However, the study also finds that female mayors help reduce this bias. In municipalities governed by female mayors, female candidates gain an additional 1 percentage point compared with other municipalities. This supports the idea of a role model effect: women in top local offices can improve the electoral prospects of other women in politics. Finally, voting patterns are not only local. The spatial analysis shows that voters are influenced by neighbouring municipalities' past and present electoral results.

4. Policy Recommendations

First, policymakers should promote young people's political participation at all levels of government. The findings suggest bleak prospects for young candidates. Parties and local authorities should invest in youth recruitment, mentoring, candidate training and visible pathways into municipal politics. This is not only a participation issue: it affects whether younger generations see their needs reflected in local policy decision-making.

Second, gender quotas should be complemented with measures that help

women access visible and powerful positions. The study shows that quotas alone do not completely eliminate the female electoral penalty. Political parties should therefore place more women in leading list positions, support women candidates during campaigns, and address informal barriers inside local party organisations. Female mayors reduce the penalty faced by female candidates, suggesting that visible leadership can change voting behaviour. Leadership programmes, cross-party networks for women in local politics, and transparent procedures for selecting mayoral candidates could help accelerate this process.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

Further Information:

Catalano, L., Iliopoulos, P., & De Witte, K. (2026). The influence of descriptive representation on voting patterns: a study of age and gender dynamics. *Local Government Studies*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03003930.2026.2680214>

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